

**MY BACKYARD IS A ROLLER COASTER: LIVED EXPERIENCES OF
PRIMIGRAVIDA DURING COVID-19 PANDEMIC**

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Abstract

Introduction: The protection of the well-being of mothers, infants, and children is a pivotal public health concern across the globe. Understanding the challenges experienced by the primigravida mothers and their mechanisms to overcome such adversities is an important topic that need to be explored.

Methods: The study employed phenomenology qualitative research design. The subjects were chosen through purposive sampling based on the following inclusion criteria: primigravida mothers in their first, second, or third trimester of pregnancy, from 20 to 30 years of age and from the Province of Ilocos Norte. The researcher constructed a semi-structured interview guide to collect pieces of information needed for this research undertaking. The entire interview was recorded and transcribed verbatim, with the transcriptions double-checked for correctness. The Thematic Analysis with the integration of the Colaizzi's seven-step process was utilized to analyze the data.

Results: Five major themes emerged from the narrations of the participants, and these are as follows: Disruption of the Tranquility of the Pregnant Life, New Challenges Caused by the Pandemic, Resilience in Managing the Crisis, and Supportive Network of Family and Friends, and Adaptation and Coping with New Health Conditions.

Conclusions: The study revealed that the COVID-19 epidemic has disrupted pregnant women's lifestyle and presented additional obstacles. Despite these challenges, the participants managed the crisis by relying on their family and friends to adjust to changing health conditions. These findings emphasize the necessity of providing pregnant women with credible information and a supportive network during the pandemic to help them manage and overcome their concerns.

Keywords: Primigravida Mothers, COVID-19 Pandemic, Phenomenology, Thematic Analysis, Experiences

Introduction

Protecting the well-being of mothers, infants, and children is a pivotal public health goal across the globe. Their state of life sketches the health of the next generation and can help predict future public health challenges for families, communities, and the health care system.

Nevertheless, health care, social policy, and the general situation were all affected by the COVID-19 pandemic, which has the potential to have an immediate effect on women's and babies' reproductive and perinatal well-being. Kotlar et al. (2021) figured out that there are both immediate and long-term implications of COVID-19 on maternal health.

Antenatal care is fundamentally the initial step toward ensuring the survival of the mother and her newborn. However, the prenatal period is similarly crucial that is often accompanied by mental distress associated with pregnancy itself. Besides the fear resulting from pregnancy, there are other several risk factors associated with high anxiety prevalence during pregnancy. Contextually, one of these factors that can affect the mental health of pregnant women is uncertainty related to catastrophic events or natural disasters like the global health crisis caused by the COVID-19 pandemic.

COVID-19 is an infectious disease caused by a new strain of coronavirus that initially began in Wuhan, China. The pandemic is an example of a natural disaster with so much global health burden. From a global perspective, the evolution of this virus resulted in some health protocols or policies such as strict social distancing, lockdowns, and the wearing of safety gears such as face masks and face shields. These protocols and policies also resulted in more restricted access to goods including access to healthcare services. On March 24, 2020, about 1.3 billion people in India were placed on a lockdown. As a result, some higher-risk groups were required to cocoon which resulted in increased social isolation. The abrupt situation increased levels of anxiety and depression among pregnant women (Ryan et al., 2020).

Moreover, the American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists (ACOG) and the Society for Maternal-Fetal Medicine shared that after lockdowns, several countries reported amplified rates of stillbirth, which may have been associated with interruptions in prenatal care and a higher frequency of home birth (Berghella & Hughes, 2021).

In the Philippines, the COVID-19 pandemic has also disrupted family planning and maternal services and its subsidiary impacts may significantly be an increase in the annual maternal mortality and unplanned pregnancies beginning in 2020 compared with the pre-COVID years. Pregnant women's utilization of facilities for ante-natal check-ups and delivery was declined due to service disruption, difficulty in commuting, and the fear of contracting COVID-19. Before COVID-19, the Philippines already recorded about 2,600 women dying every year due to complications from pregnancy or childbirth. Marquez (2020) estimated that maternal mortality cases in 2020 can increase to 670 additional deaths from the 2019 level (26 % increase).

As of this writing, the Province of Ilocos Norte had already recorded 133, 817 COVID-19 cases with 2, 404 deaths. In a more specific instance, Adriano (2020) put into the record that a pregnant Overseas Filipino Worker (OFW) from the United Arab Emirates who returned to her hometown in Barangay Catanggaran, Solsona, Ilocos Norte was found positive of the aforementioned disease. The said patient was referred to as IN-C4, a 30-year-old female. To dig deeper into the phenomenon, the researcher reached out to the woman and in a closed-door interview, she shared her testimonies about the adversities she needed to go through while carrying her child in her womb during the pandemic. She also added that the COVID-19 pandemic induced a considerable degree of fear, worry, and concern for her health and her baby.

Relatively, another pregnant woman was interviewed by the researcher to cull out her lived experiences during the pandemic. She shared that being pregnant became so stressful due to the applicable guidelines, regulations, and provisions set by the Inter-Agency Task Force for the Management of Emerging Infectious Diseases (IATF MEID), Department of Health (DOH), and Provincial Government of Ilocos Norte (PGIN). She relayed that she needed to use a face mask and face shield, get BHERT Certificate, and undergo a swab test before giving birth in a hospital.

Particularly in Ilocos Norte, a pregnant Overseas Filipino Worker from the United Arab Emirates who returned to her hometown in Solsona, was found positive of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19). The said patient was referred as INC-4, a 30-year-old female from Barangay Catangaran. The OFW was quarantined in a facility in Pampanga after arriving from the UAE. She reached Solsona on June 15 and was brought in the town's Ligtas COVID-19 facility. As the patient was preeclamptic, the Municipal Health Officer referred her to the Mariano Marcos Memorial Hospital and Medical Center (MMMH & MC) where she underwent a caesarian operation and swab testing. Her Real-Time Reverse Transcription Polymerase Chain Reaction (RT-PCR) result revealed SARS Cov-2 Viral RNA detected (Adriano, 2020).

Research Problem

This study explored the lived experiences of primigravida mothers of Ilocos Norte during the COVID-19 pandemic. It culled out the personal challenges they needed to go through and highlighted the mechanisms they employed for them to overcome such adversities. The experiences they shared were synthesized which served as the researcher's bases for developing a plan of action to address and erode the obstacles shared by the subjects.

Methods

Research Design. This study employed qualitative research design as it explored the lived experiences of primigravida during COVID-19 pandemic. It is phenomenology in nature because it sought to describe the essence of a phenomenon by exploring it from the perspective of those who have experienced it. Its goal is to describe the meaning of these experience in terms of what was experienced and how it was experienced (Neubauer et al., 2019).

Participants. This study utilized the purposive sampling (Campbell et al., 2020). There are inclusion criteria in the selection of the subjects namely: primigravida, should be on her 1st, 2nd or 3rd trimester of pregnancy, 20 to 30 years old, and from the Province of Ilocos Norte. The researcher ended up with the data gathering after reaching the point of saturation.

Research Instrument. The data-gathering instrument was an interview guide reflecting the questions developed by the researcher. These questions were written the English and were translated in Iloko. Subjects were highly encouraged to share their experiences during COVID-19 pandemic. The elicited responses of the subjects were presented into themes and sub-themes.

At the time the researcher met the point of saturation, she stopped conducting the face-to-face interview; thus, the sample or the required number of subjects was already met.

Data Analysis. Data interpretation focused on the practicality of the findings for clinical practice or move toward speculating. After gathering and organizing necessary pieces of information, a soft copy of the files for clustering and classifying data was secured. Transcript files were copied and pasted using the Microsoft Word and this allowed for the grouping of similar data into initial themes. Data analysis was done immediately after data collection using the Thematic analysis (Nowell et.al., 2017) and the Colaizzi's seven (7) steps.

Results

First Major Theme: Disruption of the Tranquility of the Pregnant Life. The first major theme that emerged from the narrations of the ten (10) subjects was “disruption of the tranquility of the pregnant life.” The pregnant women were under intense stress for the first few weeks of pregnancy. The sub-themes that emerged from the narrations of the ten subjects were the following: (1) financial constraints during pandemic; (2) patiently waiting for their turn; (3) absence from work due to the scheduled consultation; and (4) strict compliance to health protocols such as diagnostic tests for COVID-19.

Second Major Theme: New Challenges Caused by the Pandemic. The second major theme that emerged from the subjects is “new challenges caused by the pandemic.” The following sub-themes supports the existence of the major theme: (1) the need to comply to health protocols; (2) indifference of doctors in providing care; and (3) salary deduction.

Third Major Theme: Resilience in Managing the Crisis. For this major theme, it is supported by three sub-themes: (1) holistically strong; (2) being positive despite the crisis; and (3) belief in the Lord Almighty.

Fourth Major Theme: Supportive Networks of Family and Friends. In both happy and sad times, it is crucial to be surrounded by family and friends for support and comfort. Supportive interactions have been established in studies to be a powerful protective factor against mental diseases and to assist humans in improving their mental well-being. For this major theme, it is supported by the following sub-themes: (1) financial support of parents; (2) family support; (3) family consultation; and (4) friend consultation.

Fifth Major Theme: Adaptation and Coping with New Health Conditions. The fifth major theme that emerged was adaptation and coping with the new health conditions. The sub-themes that support the major theme are as follows: (1) music as an antidote to boredom; (2) use of the social media to prevent boredom; (3) vegetable gardening for food sufficiency; and (4) work and pleasure.

Discussions

Disruption of the Tranquility of the Pregnant Life. Relative to this, Mortazavi and Ghardazi (2021) disclosed that women who were pregnant at the time of the COVID-19 pandemic were under a lot of stress. As such, it is very essential for them to get a health system that is mobilized to alleviate their challenges during such difficult times. Pregnant women may benefit from stress reduction techniques like online training and counseling.

Subtheme 1 - Financial Constraints during Pandemic. The first sub-theme that emerged from the narrations of the subjects was financial constraints during pandemic. The subjects gave clear and understandable narrations that unmistakably showed the impact of the financial constraints experienced during the pandemic. Among these narrations are the following:

“It is difficult to be pregnant these days especially because we have no money for the pregnancy. But I am hoping that I will be able to go through this kind of pregnancy” – Subject 3

The findings imply that being pregnant during the COVID-19 pandemic can cause financial constraints among pregnant women. This is associated with the expense of the pregnancy as well as other added expenses due to many restrictions brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic.

Subtheme 2 - Patiently Waiting for their Turn. The second sub-theme that emerged from the subjects' testimonies was patiently waiting for their turn. While it is critical to implement policies that reduce the risk of COVID-19 transmission to pregnant women and health care providers, according to Burgess et al., (2021), health care providers and policymakers must also listen to the collective voices of women during pregnancy about how COVID-19 has affected their pregnancy, birth, and infant feeding plans, as well as their perceptions.

The sub-theme is supported by the narration of the following subject:

“We need to be patient in waiting for our turn to be seen by the doctor because of the current situation”– Subject 2

The findings imply that the subjects have experienced a situation where they are not prioritized and has many restrictions. Nevertheless, they must be provided with assistance because they are having a crisis of their own being pregnant. In this regard, one major concern of pregnant individuals with COVID-19 are their prognoses and the possibility of vertical transmission and subsequent miscarriage, malformations, fetal growth restriction and/or stillbirth (Hayakawa et al., 2020).

On the contrary, although the lockdown measures have succeeded so far in relative containment of COVID-19, the study of Muhaidat et al. (2020) suggests that there is no significant disruption to antenatal services that has occurred, and that the lockdown has not affected the wellbeing of pregnant women in several aspects.

Subtheme 3: Absence from Work due to the Scheduled Consultation. The third sub-theme that emerged from the narrations of the subjects was absence from work due to scheduled consultation. This is associated with the conclusion of Goyal, et al., (2020) which states that there is a decrease in institutional deliveries and that one-third of pregnant women had inadequate antenatal visits.

The sub-theme was supported by the narrations of one of the subjects.

“There are instances when excusing from work is difficult because of so many requirements to meet so absence from work cannot be avoided. There will be corresponding salary deductions too from leaving. But prenatal care is needed for us to ensure the health and safety of my child”
– Subject 3

The findings denote that pregnant women have various concerns and issues during the COVID-19 pandemic which includes being absent to work when they visit the doctor for consultation. Being absent causes them mental stress since this is also tantamount to salary deduction. For pregnant women during the pandemic, there is a need to help ensure that they experience a comfortable pregnancy and delivery even if this means sacrificing one's attendance to work.

Subtheme 4: Diagnostic tests for COVID-19. Diagnostic testing for COVID-19 identified was the fourth sub-theme that emerged from the subjects' narratives. For the etiological diagnosis of SARS-CoV-2 infection, the real-time reverse transcription (RT-PCR) assay remains the molecular test of choice (Tang, et.al., 2020). The sub-theme is supported by the various narrations of the subjects. For example:

“We have to undergo COVID-19 test ma’am before we can enter the hospital for the consultation” – Subject 8

According to Orisaka et al., (2020), in low-prevalence areas of COVID-19, universal screening of pregnant women may not be essential and should not be mandatory. Similarly, selective testing of pregnant women at high risk, such as those who have any symptoms, a history of close contact with someone who has COVID-19, recent travel/arrival from a high-prevalence area, and those who are concerned about the possibility of having COVID-19, might be reasonable. It is also important to be ready to conduct universal screening of pregnant women at any moment if the local prevalence of SARS-CoV-2 infection rises.

Second Major Theme: New Challenges Caused by the Pandemic

Subtheme 1 - The Need to Comply to Health Protocols. Compliance with health protocols is the first sub-theme. Pregnant women must follow health measures to prevent the novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV) from spreading through respiratory droplets. Scientifically, the virus can stay active for hours to days on many surfaces under artificial conditions, therefore contacting the face or mucosal surfaces with contaminated hands may cause infection (Dzinamarira et al., 2021). Droplets can pollute up to 6 feet (91.44 cm) from the source (Kord et al., 2020). This sub-theme is supported by narration of the following participant:

“These times are very difficult for us because of many health protocols to follow. We need to use face mask and face shields before we enter in hospitals or wherever we go.” – Subject 2

The abovementioned declarations from the subjects tell a tale of trials on how they were able to battle against the pandemic during their pregnancy. They have specified challenges that contributed to their mental distress. It can be sensed from their testimonies that following health protocols became an unfriendly experience for them during the said state of their lives.

Subtheme 2: Indifference of Doctors in Providing Care. The second sub-theme that supports the major theme is the indifference of the doctors in providing care. The sub-theme is supported by the narrations of the subjects. For example:

“We waited for long hours for the doctor to see us. They said that they have still a lot of patients.” – Subject 7

The findings suggest pregnant women during the COVID-19 pandemic were not given safe and excellent care. This contradicts Tuncalp et al. (2015), who argue that every pregnant woman and newborn needs professional birth care with evidence-based methods in a humane, supportive environment to eradicate unnecessary maternal and newborn morbidity and mortality. Quality care needs effective clinical and non-clinical interventions, reinforced health infrastructure, and optimal skills and attitude of health workers, resulting in improved health outcomes and positive experiences for women and providers. The right to health and justice and dignity for women and children depend on quality of care.

Subtheme 3: Salary deduction. The third sub-theme that supports the major theme is salary deduction. This is supported by the narrations of the following subjects:

“My salary will be deducted when we absent ourselves from work. But it is needed for us to attend prenatal consultation so that my baby will remain healthy” – Subject 3

Most industries were affected by the COVID-19 pandemic, including entertainment, hospitality, sports, travel, and others. According to Rubeena and Naz (2020), most people endure stress-related consequences because of unemployment, which has been degrading people's mental health. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, there is financial deprivation all throughout the world, which raises the unemployment rate.

Third Major Theme: Resilience in Managing the Crisis

Subtheme 1: Holistically strong. The first theme that emerged from the narrations of the subjects was being holistically strong. From the narrations of the subjects, the evidence is clear that pregnant women during the pandemic expresses their views that there is a need to be holistically strong. The following testimonies prove this claim:

“I need to be strong emotionally, physically, and mentally at these times.” – Subject 6

The findings suggest pregnant women should be holistically strong during the health crises. Naurin et al. (2020) found that early in the pandemic, pregnant women worried about their own and their family's health. Due to the COVID-19 epidemic, pregnant women and their partners need more health knowledge. Anxiety may affect pregnancy outcomes and long-term health. The report advised healthcare systems to pre-arrange follow-up consultations with these families.

Subtheme 2: Being positive despite the crisis. The second theme that emerged from the narrations of the subjects was being positive despite the crisis. This commendable perception of pregnant women in overcoming the adversities brought by the pandemic during their pregnancy can be sensed from the following statements:

“What I do is to stay optimistic, I always remember to stay positive even if there is a pandemic, and find time to relax, watch TV and find productive work and still continue to be positive.” – Subject 7

The narrations of the subjects imply that pregnant women should be optimistic even at times of crisis since mental health is as important as physical health. Their testimonies prove that a positive mind is a necessity to overcome the burden of the health crisis.

Subtheme 3: Belief in Lord Almighty. The third sub-theme that emerged from the narrations of the subjects was belief in the Lord Almighty. This sub-theme is supported by the following statements from the subjects:

“There are so many ways to cope with this situation. But the most important thing to do is to pray that this will end soon. We believe that God will always be there for us.” – Subject 9

The results suggest that pregnant women are humble enough to pray to the Lord Almighty. According to a by Simão et al., (2016), prayer was a positive factor, reducing the anxiety of

mothers of children with cancer, reducing the level of concern of subjects who believe in a solution to their problem, and improving the physical functioning of patients who believe in prayer. Prayer should be part of holistic nursing care for patients' well-being.

Fourth Major Theme: Supportive Networks of Family and Friends

Subtheme 1: Financial support of parents and family. The first sub-theme that emerged from the narrations of the subjects is the financial support of their parents.

This sub-theme is supported by the narrations of the following subjects:

“Money is not a problem because our parents continue to extend help to us.”– Subject 8

This finding implies that parents continue to provide financial support to their children because they are waiting for their grandchild to be born and the thought of their birth is a form of joy and happiness to them. Likewise, it implies family support whether financially or emotionally in which it is very crucial in this time of pandemic.

Subtheme 2: Family support. The second sub- theme that emerged from the narrations of the subjects is the family support. Family support plays an important part on pregnant women's mental health during the COVID-19 pandemic. Better family support can help improve the mental health of pregnant women (Wang et.al., 2021)

This sub-theme is supported by the narrations of the following subjects:

“Our situation is very hard, but we need to be strong. We can't do anything but to adapt to the present situation. What is important is that there are those persons who supports me and my pregnancy. My family and friends are very supportive of my pregnancy that is why I am very thankful for them.”– Subject 9

COVID-19 can cause psychological and physical crises. COVID-19 enhanced psychological suffering in clinical and general populations. Women are more likely than men to suffer psychological damage after disasters (Wang et al., 2021).

Subtheme 3: Family consultation. The third sub-theme that emerged from the narrations of the subjects is the involvement of their family. The sub-theme is supported by the following statements:

“With these things that are happening, I would visit my mother and my elder sister and will inquire from them so that I know what will I do.”
– Subject 3

The findings imply that the subjects can still communicate and consult their family with regards to their experience of pregnancy, which became more challenging due to the COVID-19 pandemic. According to Wang et al., (2021), women who have supportive networks of friends and family may experience less stress and have better mental health conditions. Conversely, poor family relationships and social support might be associated with depressive symptoms.

Subtheme 4: Friend consultation. The fourth sub-theme that emerged from the narrations of the subjects is the presence of their friends whom they could reach out. The sub-theme is supported by the narrations of the subjects:

“At times, I will visit my friend who gave birth last year for me to know what to do especially at this time of the pandemic.”– Subject 1

The findings suggest that pregnant people had friends to talk to during the pandemic. Technically, pregnant women need others to listen to their struggles and achievements. This may help a pregnant lady survive the pandemic.

Fifth Major Theme: Adaptation and Coping with New Health Conditions

According to Kim et., al. (2022), the COVID-19 pandemic continues to pose an unprecedented challenge for the world as people strive to cope with this significant threat to their well-being. COVID-19, due to its particularly contagious nature and mortality rate, has induced feelings of fear and insecurity among the population.

Subtheme 1: Music as an antidote to boredom. During the COVID-19 pandemic, pregnant women used music to combat boredom. Sirak (2017) suggests using music prenatally to bond and relax newborns.

The sub-theme is supported by the following statements of the subjects:

“I listen to music, because I am quite good in singing, I can also play the guitar ma’am to reduce my stress. I can also compose songs because it is another source of my livelihood” – Subject 8

Despite the COVID-19 pandemic, pregnant women use music to avoid boredom and relax. Carolan et al. (2017) found that music lowered anxiety and cortisol levels in pregnant women before amniocentesis.

Subtheme 2: Use of the social media to prevent boredom. The second theme that emerged from the narrations of the subjects was their engagement on the use of social media to prevent boredom. This can be reflected from the following affirmations:

“The internet signal is good ma’am, so I would chat or TikTok, and I would feel good ma’am”– Subject 8

These narrations imply that pregnant women use various social media platforms for entertainment purposes to prevent boredom. Social media play an important part in communication with those far away, allowing people who are quarantined or under lockdowns to update their loved ones about their situation and reassure them that they are well.

Subtheme 3: Vegetable gardening for food sufficiency. The third theme that emerged from the narrations of the subjects is that they manage their backyard by planting vegetables for their needs for food. According to Ferdous and Datta (2016), vegetable gardening increases food security and to reduce poverty and malnutrition. The sub-theme is supported by the narrations of the following participant:

“I plant and propagate crops in our yard ma’am, so we have something to get from for our food”– Subject 5

Corley, et al. (2021) found that gardens, parks, forests, and fields provide health benefits. Green areas and nature can relieve stress, boost mood, increase life satisfaction, and avoid mental health issues. Spending time in nature also improves sleep quality, physical health, and socialization.

Subtheme 4: Work and pleasure. The fourth theme that emerged from the narrations of the subjects was that the subjects continue to work and do pleasure. According to Vyas and Butakhieo (2021), working and having pleasure at home could also be effective. Working remotely at home has been adopted by governments and organizations to contain the spread of the virus.

The sub-theme is supported by the following testimonies of the subjects:

“..I watch TV, I plant, go to the fields, or do any other works ma’am, so that I will not be stressed and will not keep thinking of my situation being pregnant”– Subject 10

The findings suggest that pregnant women can be productive during pandemic lockdowns and quarantines. The findings also suggest that pregnant women can work in different fields during the pandemic to avoid boredom from lockdowns and quarantines.

Conclusion

It is the universal role of the nurse to provide nursing care to all clients regardless of the condition, even during a COVID-19 pandemic, where there is a threat of the transmission of the virus. It is difficult but rewarding to provide nursing care to pregnant women during this health crisis. It is concluded that pregnant women experienced adversities pertaining to their daily activities, prenatal care, and financial constraints due to the expenses of the pregnancy and delivery. Subjects have varied experiences summarized in terms of the following major themes: Disruption of the Tranquility of the Pregnant Life, New Challenges Caused by the Pandemic, and Supportive Network of Family and Friends. On the other hand, the subjects differ in their experiences on two major themes: Adaptation and Coping with New Health Conditions, and Resilience in Managing the Crisis.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions drawn, the following recommendations are offered: (1) The developed action plan for primigravida mothers during the COVID-19 pandemic can be presented to the PGIN for possible adaptation, (2) The Department of Nursing and the Master of Arts in Nursing can consider initiating extension programs regarding Maternal and Child Care amidst the COVID-19 Pandemic, (3) Specialty organizations such as Maternal and Child Nurses Association of the Philippines (MCNAP) may support nurses on the implementation of such program for Maternal and Child Care, and (4) the proposed Action Plan may be evaluated after a year to determine its extent of implementation and impact.

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